

THE FREEDOM OF INFORMATION IN THE USA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7659418>

Abstract: The study attempts to investigate the effect of disclosure to information and the respond to the non-legal acts towards to journalists. In addition, the study focused on determining collected samples due to the legal documents. And according to the comparison the whole result and conclusion were made.

Key words: FOIA, amendment, constitutions, United States, public information, documents, law, compensation, truthfulness, clarification, forbidden actions, journalists, mass media, ethics of journalism.

Most freedom of information laws according to their state has general principles and characteristics. Because many recent laws of this kind have been modeled on the US Federal Freedom of Information Act (FOIA), as well as, it will be taken as an example of other acts. President Lyndon Johnson signed FOIA on July 4, 1966. Contrary to its name, this law did not formally create a right of access to information but merely asserted a presumption of a right of access to existing materials in print or digital form owned by the executive branch of government, represented by ministries, departments, and regulatory commissions, as well as government-controlled corporations. These included, for example, the State Department, the Ministries of Defense and Justice, the Federal Bureau of Investigation, the Central Intelligence Agency, and many other agencies. Unlike the laws of countries such as Ireland, the American FOIA does not contain a list of names of agencies subject to its application, but simultaneously does not make a categorical exception for intelligence and security agencies, as in the UK. However, FOIA does not apply to the legislative and judicial branches of government. Access to records held by state and local governments is subject to state open government laws. In the United States, as in most countries, anyone can apply under the FOIA. It does not require citizenship or permanent residence, and access is open to everyone, not just journalists. FOIA applicants are encouraged to use both physical and virtual government reading rooms to gain seamless access to materials already declassified under so-called E-FOIA initiatives or released to the public through prior requests. They are also encouraged to contact the agency's FOIA Commissioner prior to submitting a formal FOIA request to discuss informally what types of archival material can be obtained upon request. In the United

States, no special form is required to submit a FOIA request, a simple letter to the appropriate FOIA Commissioner clearly describing the material requested is sufficient. Most departments accept requests both in writing and via the Internet.

However, despite the presumption of openness, almost any freedom of information law provides for exceptions - categories of documents that can be legally denied access. The American FOIA provides for nine exceptions, which, according to the provisions of the law itself and clarifications of the Department of Justice, should be interpreted in a narrow case:

- a. national security;
- b. internal rules and office procedures of the agency;
- c. memos for internal circulation (working papers, reports and studies prepared as part of the agency's decision-making process);
- d. professional secrecy;
- e. materials classified under another federal law;
- f. law enforcement materials;
- g. bank accounting documentation;
- h. data on oil and gas fields;
- i. materials containing information, the disclosure of which would result in an unreasonable violation of privacy.

Most of these exceptions are optional. The Office may make the requested materials available if it determines that the public interest in disclosing the information outweighs any potential harm. The Office must be prepared to provide a compelling justification for any exception and to deny access to only the statutory portion of any document without preventing access to the remainder. Grounds for denying access to a particular document may eventually disappear. If the requests relate to classified documents, applicants may, if they wish, appeal the denial to a special appeals panel, which will determine whether the document can be declassified. In some countries, but not the United States, public information laws prohibit certain categories of information from being classified. Freedom of information is constitutional law in about 80 countries. Swedish law on the seal of 1766, regarded by many as the first freedom of information legislation, included in the country's constitution. Some more long-standing constitutions amended for the right to receiving the information. Many developing democracies in Central and Eastern Europe and Latin America included in the text of their new constitutions' provisions on access to information. But even if the constitutions do not clearly contain formulated

provisions in this regard, constitutional courts of a number of countries, including the South Korea, Japan and Israel concluded that the right to freedom of speech or of the press implies the right to access to the information.

There is no non-disclosure law in the United States state secrets similar to those that exist in many other countries, however, access to legally classified documents may be closed by presidential decree. The applicant has the right to appeal the refusal. According to FOIA, as well as relevant laws in most countries, this process starts with requirements to consider the complaint within the departments. Sometimes the use of such tactics results in permission to access the data. The next step is to appeal to outside departments. In the United States, this means suing in federal district court the possibility of appeal to the federal appellate courts and even the Supreme Court USA. In other countries and in some US states the applicant may appeal to the Ombudsman, authorized to deal with complaints relating to FOIA, or to an independent information tribunal or commissions. But even in these jurisdictions, the final proceedings take place at the national level. In the event of a win, the complainant not only obtains access to the documents requested by him but also receives compensation for the fees of his lawyers. In some states of the United States and in many other countries, the courts are empowered to impose sanctions on government departments and their employees who deliberately deny requests for documents in violation of the law. Sanctions may be expressed in monetary fines, and in rare, especially egregious cases, even in prison. Most codes of ethics for journalists emphasize the importance of following truthfulness, monitor the authenticity transmitted information. "Seek the truth and pass on her" – this is the main, core principle of the Code ethical standards of the Society for Professional journalists. Code of Conduct for UK Editors also prioritizes truthfulness, proclaiming: "The press should under no circumstances publish false, misleading or false information, including graphics. Universal ethical principle number one to express in a simple wording: a journalist does not under what circumstances should not publish deliberate lie. This requirement is not so easy to fulfill in all cases. Before publishing the material, the journalist, should definitely do everything possible to make sure it matches reality. But in time may be discovered facts that refute the already published material. In this case, the responsible news organization without delay publishes an amendment or clarification. Obviously, journalists should not copy previous news and do plagiarism, i.e. enjoy the fruits of someone else's labor without indicating the source. It is forbidden to invent quotes and reprint someone else's material without prior permission of the

author. There are five ethics of journalism. Five principles of information of ethical journalism are:

- a. truth and accuracy
- b. independence
- c. fairness and impartiality
- d. humanity
- e. accountability

These standards encourage all journalists to become more sociable and provide true information to the audience. Moreover, this "Media esthetics" is known as a "Code of esthetics" or "Canons of journalism" in many countries.

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